

Effects Of Pituitary Hormone And Condition Factor (Kn) On Post –Embryonic Development In Cirrhina Mrigala (Ham.)

Paper Id : 19967 Submission Date : 2023-07-13 Acceptance Date : 2023-07-22 Publication Date : 2023-07-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15305421

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Abstract

The present study has been made on effect of pituitary hormone and condition factor on Cirrhina Mrigala (Ham.) for about one month and revealed faster post-embryonic development which is correlated with growth as against the control experiments. 2.5 mg/lit. dose of Pituitary proved suitable in all respect. Mortality figure comes out 4,5,7 and 12 for 0.0mg/lit, 1.5mg/lit.,2.5mg/lit. and 3.5mg/lit. dose treatment respectively. The study revealed that there was a close relationship between growth and development. There is a very important aspect of morph metrical parameters showed marked changes in all Pituitary hormone treated experiment (Cultural investigation). Study suggests that most powerful hormone therapy may prove in the culture of Cirrhina Mrigala (Ham.)

Keywords Pituitary Hormone, Post-embryonic Development, Condition Factor (Kn), Cirrhina Mrigala (Ham.).

Introduction

Pituitary hormone plays an important role in the maturation of gonads and body growth of fish. The growth hormone (Somatotropin) of the pituitary gland also influences protein, carbohydrate and fate metabolism to a great extent (Knobil et. al.,(1957). The effect of pituitary hormone treatment on the post-embryonic development of Cirrhina Mrigala (Ham.) is not yet fully known and needs further investigation.

Objective of study

With the view point in the present communication an efforts is made to work out the optimum dose of hormone which could be able to affect some aspects of post-embryonic development in a positive direction, as pituitary hormone treatment has been shown to promote post-embryonic development, growth ,condition factor and survival in several fish species.

Review of Literature

Some of the important contributions on the said field of studies are from Land grebe (1941); Baldwin et. al.(1942); Swift (1954); Knobil et.al.(1957); Atz et. al. (1977); Das et. al.(1962); Tata (1968); Liley et.al.(1969); Yamazaki (1976); Clarke et.al.(1977); Adelman (1982); Joss (1985); Mchean et. al.(1990); Lakra et. al.(1996); Wilson et. al. (1998); Brzuska et. al. (1999); Roy et. al. (2000); Hasan et. al.(2021); Islam et. al. (2021) and Romain Fontaine et. al. (2022).

Main Text

The hatchlings (3-4 days old) of Cirrhina mrigala (Ham.) were collected from fish farm in the close vicinity of Raebareli. The hatchlings for consecutive development stages were brought to laboratory and transferred to plastic trough under observation. In each experimental trough, 20 specimens were placed on the basis of proper stocking density (Approximately 2 fish /lit.). The physico-chemical conditions of the experimental troughs were maintained merely natural by the use of sand particles, hydrilla plant, zoo and phytoplanktons. Hitachi readymade food pellets in quantity were also given at regular intervals to all the experimental larvae. The pituitary hormone doses of 1.5mg/lit, 2.5mg/lit. and 3.5mg/lit concentration were prepared by pituitary extract alcoholic method from the common carp and in each trough one kind of them was added.

By random sampling five specimens from each kind of experiment and control were taken out for derivation of mean standard under different aspects of studies on post- embryonic development at a successive time period 30 days in order to study later developmental stages. Morphometrical parameters of the larvae were recorded with the help of Vernier Calipers and waning balance machine at the end of the experiments.

Condition factor on the post embryonic development and growth was calculated on the basis of the following equation:-

$$K_n = \frac{W \times 10^5}{L^3}$$

Where, K_n = Condition factor

W = weight of fish

L = Length of fish

10^5 = Bringing the condition factor (near the unit (Carlander, 1970)

Result and Discussion

On the perusal of the parameters indicated in the Table 1, it can be concluded that a dose 2.5mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 1, 2 & Table 1).

Table-1

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	1.5mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	2.5mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	3.5mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.048	23.712 \pm 0.050	30.867 \pm 0.119	30.067 \pm 0.039
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.010	14.507 \pm 0.379	19.847 \pm 0.045	19.067 \pm 0.039
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.036	06.857 \pm 0.057	07.392 \pm 0.094	07.067 \pm 0.039
4	Distance Between snout and anal pore	14.892 \pm 0.061	16.475 \pm 0.136	20.417 \pm 0.143	20.117 \pm 0.067
5	Distance Between snout and anal fin base	16.677 \pm 0.090	16.807 \pm 0.053	24.192 \pm 0.044	23.562 \pm 0.302
6	Distance Between snout and dorsal fin base	13.552 \pm 0.068	16.457 \pm 0.147	18.622 \pm 0.205	19.062 \pm 0.039
7	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.109	05.432 \pm 0.150	06.437 \pm 0.088	06.262 \pm 0.037
8	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.074	06.747 \pm 0.105	08.832 \pm 0.035	08.362 \pm 0.083
9	Body Weight	88.867	106.392	109.867	107.378
10	Condition Factor	0.845	0.797	0.373	0.394
11	Mortality	Four	Five	Seven	Twelve

The general morphometrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae revealed that a dose of 2.5 mg/lit. , standard length 30.867mm; body length 19.847mm; head length 7.392mm; distance between snout and anal pore 20.417mm; distance between snout and anal fin base 24.192mm; distance between a snout and dorsal fin base 18.622mm; height of the body at anal fin base 6.437mm; height of the body at dorsal fin base 8.832mm; and body weight 109.867mg was observed , which is significant. In terms of the best estimated in correspondence to post-embryonic development.

It has also been marked those early developmental periods when morphogenesis is on its full swing, the pituitary treatment resulted into maximum increment in standard body length at 2.5mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 1.5mg/lit; 2.5mg/lit. and 3.5mg/lit. dose treatment (Table 1)

The application of P2 (2.5mg/Lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment prove to be the best in term of total length in comparison to control and other pituitary doses.

Condition factor is calculated for different doses of pituitary hormone in treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 2 the condition factor showed decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of minimum condition factor at P1(1.5mg/lit.) provide the values as 0.797 for 30 days experiment.

Conclusion

Therefore, 2.5 mg/lit. dose was calculated to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Principal, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli for providing the essential research facilities during this investigation.

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